

Thus

$$\lim_{c \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{D'}{C^{1/2}} = \frac{\partial \ln \gamma_{\pm}}{2 \partial C^{1/2}} = \frac{2.3026 \partial \log \gamma_{\pm}}{2 \partial C^{1/2}} \right. \\ \left. = -\frac{2.3026}{2} S_{(r)} \right] \quad (6)$$

By plotting $D'/C^{1/2}$ vs $C^{1/2}$ to this limiting value, the activity coefficient can be computed from equation (4) by graphical integration method.

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Ultrasonic Velocity of Calcium Soap Solutions

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THE ultrasonic measurements have been used for determining the ion-solvent interaction and solvation number¹⁻⁵ in aqueous media but less attention has been paid to the solvation of ions in non-aqueous media.

The present work deals with the ultrasonic measurements of the solutions of calcium soaps (caprate and laurate) in a mixture of 50% chloroform and 50% propylene glycol (v/v) and the results have been used to calculate the various acoustical and physicochemical parameters of these soap solutions.

Experimental

Calcium soaps were prepared by the metathesis of the corresponding potassium soap with aqueous solution of calcium acetate. The purity of the soaps was checked by determining their melting points and elemental analysis.

The ultrasonic velocity was determined by Ultrasonic Interferometer (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi) at a frequency of 4 MHz with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5\%$ at $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$. The densities of the solvent and solutions of calcium soaps were determined by means of a pycnometer.

The specific acoustic impedance⁶ (Z), intermolecular free length⁷ (L_f), adiabatic compressibility (β), apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_k), apparent molal volume⁸ (ϕ_v), molar sound velocity (R) and primary solvation number⁹ (S_n) have been calculated by using the relationships,

$$Z = \rho v \quad (1)$$

$$\beta = v^{-2} \rho^{-1} \quad (2)$$

$$L_f = K \sqrt{\beta} \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_k = \frac{1000}{C\rho_0} (\rho_0\beta - \beta_0\rho) + \frac{\beta_0 M}{\rho_0} \quad (4)$$

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000}{C\rho_0} (\rho_0 - \rho) + \frac{M}{\rho_0} \quad (5)$$

$$R = \frac{\overline{M}}{\rho} v^{1/3} \quad (6)$$

$$\overline{M} = \frac{n_0 M_0 + nM}{n_0 + n}$$

$$S_n = \frac{n_0}{n} \left[1 - \frac{V\beta}{n_0 V_0 \beta_0} \right] \quad (7)$$

where, ρ_0, ρ ; β_0, β ; n_0, n ; M_0, M and V_0 and V are the density, adiabatic compressibility, number of mole, molecular weight and molar volume of solvent and solute, respectively, and K, C and v are the temperature dependent Jacobson's constant, concentration (g mol dm⁻³) and ultrasonic velocity, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The results of ultrasonic velocity and various acoustical parameters for the solutions of calcium soaps in a mixture of 50% chloroform and 50% propylene glycol are recorded in Tables 1 and 2. The variation of ultrasonic velocity with concentration is

$$(dv/dc) = -v/2[1/\rho(d\rho/dc) + 1/\beta(d\beta/dc)]$$

The negative values of $1/\beta(d\beta/dc)$ are higher than positive values of $1/\rho(d\rho/dc)$ for the solutions of calcium soaps, (dv/dc) is positive which is in agreement with the results of other workers¹⁰⁻¹² reported for electrolytic solutions.

The plots of v, β, L_f and Z vs C , soap concentration, are characterised by an intersection of two straight lines at a concentration which corresponds to the critical micelle concentration, (CMC) of calcium soaps (caprate = $12.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and laurate = $8.4 \times 10^{-3} M$). The variation of ultrasonic velocity

TABLE 1—ULTRASONIC VELOCITY AND OTHER ACOUSTIC PARAMETERS OF CALCIUM LAURATE IN 50% CHLOROFORM AND 50% PROPYLENE GLYCOL MIXTURE (v/v) AT $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Sl. no.	$C \times 10^4$ g mol dm ⁻³	d g mol ⁻¹	v $\times 10^{-5}$ cm s ⁻¹	β $\times 10^{11}$ cm ² dyne ⁻¹	L_t Å	Z $\times 10^{-5}$ (cgs unit)	ϕ_k $\times 10^7$	S_n	ϕ_v $\times 10^{-3}$	R $\times 10^{-1}$ cm s ⁻¹
1.	1.0	1.067 4	1.410	4.712	0.441	1.505	-7.219	14.75	-1.652	473.39
2.	4.0	1.071 5	1.428	4.563	0.434	1.530	-5.822	12.27	-1.065	478.18
3.	7.0	1.074 6	1.446	4.451	0.428	1.554	-5.046	10.70	-0.847	483.32
4.	10.0	1.075 8	1.459	4.367	0.424	1.570	-4.365	9.43	-0.581	488.74
5.	13.0	1.076 9	1.470	4.297	0.421	1.583	-3.890	8.49	-0.431	493.97
6.	16.0	1.077 6	1.481	4.231	0.418	1.596	-3.558	7.85	-0.314	499.36
7.	19.0	1.078 8	1.490	4.175	0.415	1.607	-3.286	7.29	-0.258	504.27
8.	21.0	1.079 7	1.493	4.127	0.412	1.617	-3.204	7.12	-0.235	507.72
9.	24.0	1.080 4	1.509	4.065	0.409	1.630	-3.049	6.83	-0.181	513.06
10.	25.0	1.081 5	1.512	4.045	0.408	1.635	-3.017	6.74	-0.198	514.36

TABLE 2—ULTRASONIC VELOCITY AND OTHER ACOUSTIC PARAMETERS OF CALCIUM CAPRATE IN 50% CHLOROFORM AND 50% PROPYLENE GLYCOL MIXTURE (v/v) AT $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Sl. no.	$C \times 10^3$ g mol ⁻¹ dm ⁻³	d g ml ⁻¹	v $\times 10^5$ cm s ⁻¹	β $\times 10^{11}$ cm ² dyne ⁻¹	L_t Å	Z $\times 10^{-5}$ (cgs unit)	ϕ_k $\times 10^7$	S_n	ϕ_v $\times 10^{-3}$	R $\times 10^{-1}$ cm s ⁻¹
1.	1.0	1.067 4	1.409	4.719	0.441	1.504	-6.494	13.10	-1.425	473.07
2.	4.0	1.069 8	1.418	4.649	0.438	1.517	-3.513	7.31	-0.627	476.79
3.	7.0	1.072 7	1.427	4.578	0.434	1.531	-3.141	6.51	-0.526	480.27
4.	10.0	1.075 1	1.431	4.542	0.433	1.538	-2.617	5.39	-0.458	483.37
5.	13.0	1.077 0	1.443	4.459	0.429	1.554	-2.674	5.62	-0.442	487.58
6.	16.0	1.077 5	1.449	4.420	0.427	1.561	-2.398	5.13	-0.393	491.73
7.	19.0	1.078 0	1.454	4.388	0.425	1.567	-2.175	4.70	-0.253	495.75
8.	22.0	1.078 9	1.459	4.354	0.424	1.574	-2.026	4.42	-0.204	499.57
9.	25.0	1.079 2	1.464	4.323	0.422	1.580	-1.890	4.17	-0.155	503.65
10.	33.3	1.080 9	1.477	4.241	0.418	1.596	-1.644	3.70	-0.075	514.34

with soap concentration below the CMC follows the relationship,

$$v = v_0 + GC$$

where, v_0 is the ultrasonic velocity in the solvent and G is the Garnsey's constant. The calculated values of G for calcium caprate and laurate are 3.2×10^5 and 6.0×10^5 , respectively.

The adiabatic compressibility of the solutions of calcium soaps is found to obey Bachem's relationship¹³,

$$\beta = \beta_0 + AC + BC^{3/2}$$

The values of constants A (-4.5×10^{-10} and -7.5×10^{-10}) and B (20.0×10^{-10} and 35.0×10^{-10}) for calcium caprate and laurate, respectively, have been obtained from the intercept and slope of the plots of $(\beta - \beta_0)/C$ vs \sqrt{C} . The decrease in the values of β and L_t with the increase in ultrasonic velocity indicates that there is a significant interaction between soap and solvent molecules due to which the structural arrangement is considerably affected¹⁴.

The plots of ϕ_k vs \sqrt{C} and ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} exhibit a break at a concentration which corresponds to the CMC of these soaps, and the values of ϕ_k^0 and ϕ_v^0 have been obtained by extrapolation of these plots below the CMC to zero concentration. The limiting values of apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_k^0) and apparent molal volume (ϕ_v^0) have been found to be -7.90×10^{-7} and -1.89×10^3 , and -8.60×10^{-7} and -2.22×10^3 for calcium caprate and laurate,

respectively. The results are in agreement with that reported by Masson¹⁵ for electrolytic solutions.

The value of molar sound velocity (R) increases linearly with increasing soap concentration. The solvation number (S_n) of calcium soap solution in a mixture of 50% chloroform and 50% propylene glycol decreases with the increase in the soap concentrations. The variation in the values of solvation number with concentration is in agreement with the results proposed by Prakash *et al.*¹⁶ for the solution of lanthanum nitrate in methanol and ethanol. The results show that the adiabatic compressibility, intermolecular free length and solvation number decrease, while the specific acoustic impedance, apparent molal compressibility, apparent molal volume and molar sound velocity increase with increasing soap concentration.

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Studies on Mechanism of Ylide Initiated Radical Copolymerisation of Methyl Methacrylate with Styrene

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THREE mechanisms, namely (i) ternary molecular complex, (ii) cross-propagation and (iii) complexed radical, have been proposed for the copolymerisation of vinyl monomers in presence of Lewis acids. The copolymerisation of such monomers in the presence of ylide is relatively new discipline of polymer science and a few publications in this area have recently¹⁻⁴ appeared.

Experimental

The experimental details for present system have already been published elsewhere⁵. The polymerisations were carried out at 60° by employing modified dilatometric apparatus⁶ for 3 h under an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The dilatometer was filled with the required amount of monomer and β -picolinium-*p*-chlorophenacylide (β -PCPY) in carbon tetrachloride. The copolymer was fractionated with acetonitrile and cyclohexane to remove homopolymers of methyl methacrylate (MMA) and styrene (Sty), respectively, but no detectable weight loss has been observed. The nmr, ir and esr spectra have been recorded with Varian 100 HA spectrometer, Perkin-Elmer 377, and E-line century series 109 (X-band) spectrometers, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic data⁵

$$R_p \propto [\beta\text{-PCPY}]^{0.6} [\text{MMA}]^{0.75} \frac{1}{[\text{Sty}]^{0.4}}$$

inhibitory effect of hydroquinone and gyromagnetic value indicate that copolymerisation of MMA with Sty, initiated by β -PCPY (ylide), proceeds by a free radical mechanism.

The nmr spectra have been used to elucidate the composition and reactivity ratio of copolymers. The peak area due to phenyl protons of Sty and methoxy protons of MMA have been used to calculate the copolymer composition, which helped to evaluate reactivity ratio using Fineman-Ross method as 0.22 (r_1) and 0.30 (r_2) for the present system. These values match well with those

reported for radical copolymerisation⁷. No detectable weight loss and reactivity ratio supports the alternate nature of copolymer. The esr spectra (Fig. 1) of polymerisation mixture shows characteristic band at 3300 gauss, which confirms radical mode of polymerisation. The gyromagnetic ratio (g) calculated is 2.002.

Fig. 1. Esr spectra of polymerisation mixture (β -PCPY, AN and Sty in CCl_4); scan range = 5 kG, field set = 3300 G, modulation amplitude = 2×1 G, modulation frequency = 100 kHz, temp. = 20°, and microwave frequency = 9.385 GHz.

In case of ternary molecular complex (charge transfer complex) mechanism, it is well reported that electron-acceptor monomer forms binary complex⁸ with Lewis acid. This complex in turn forms charge transfer complex with electron-donor monomer as evidenced by the appearance of a new absorption band⁹ in the range of 300–360 nm in uv spectrum in case of copolymerisation of MMA with Sty.

In the present case, a comparison of ir spectra of polymerisation content (Fig 2) (β -PCPY with MMA in CCl_4) and MMA show that there is no shifting in the position of bands due to ester group. This rules out the possibility of formation of complex between β -PCPY and MMA. Similarly, a comparative study of uv spectra of polymerisation mixture showed no additional absorption band at 300–360 nm, which excludes the possibility of formation of charge transfer complex. Therefore, the present system does not proceed through charge transfer complex mechanism.

In case of radical complex mechanism, the radical end of the acceptor monomer unit is postulated to be stabilised by complexing with Lewis acid and to be capped with the donor monomer